

Chelyshkov wavelets for numerical approximation of fractional optimal control problems

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Abstract

In the present study, wavelets method is applied for solving a class of fractional optimal control problems (FOCPs). The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of the Chelyshkov wavelets and the Legendre-Gauss quadrature formula are used for reducing such problems into those consisting of systems of easily solvable algebraic equations. The effectiveness and validity of the new methodology are illustrated by three examples, in addition our findings in comparison with the existing results show the preference of presented method.

Keywords: Fractional optimal control, Chelyshkov wavelets, Fractional integral operator, Numerical method

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1 Introduction

Optimal control problems represent a set of differential equations describing the paths of the control variables that minimize a function of the state and control variables. The optimal control problems in which the criterion or the differential equations of the dynamic systems display at least one fractional derivative lead to fractional optimal control problems (FOCPs). In recent years, FOCPs have gained importance due to their many applications in various fields. To mention a few, FOCPs have been used in the analog fractional-order controller in temperature and motor control applications, a fractional adaptation scheme for lateral control of an autonomous guided vehicle, fractional control of heat diffusion systems, and a fractional-order HIV-immune system with memory. Most FOCPs do not have exact analytic solutions because the dynamic constraints of this problem involve fractional differential equations; therefore, numerical methods must be used for solving them. For example Bernstein polynomials, Bernoulli wavelets, fractional-order Boubaker functions, hybrid functions, Chebyshev-Legendre operational technique, Generalized fractional-order Bernoulli-Legendre functions ([4], [5]).

¹speaker

2 Preliminaries and notations

In this section, we present some basic definitions and properties of fractional derivative and integrals which are further used in this paper.

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator of order ν is defined by means of [4]

$${}^R I_t^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\nu)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{\nu-1} f(\tau) d\tau, \quad t > 0.$$

Definition 2.2. The Caputo fractional derivative operator of order ν is defined by means of [4]

$${}^C D_t^\nu f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\nu)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{n-\nu-1} f^{(n)}(\tau) d\tau, \quad n - 1 < \nu \leq n.$$

Proposition 2.3. *The Caputo fractional derivatives and Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals satisfies the following properties:*

1. ${}^C D_t^\nu {}^R I_t^\nu f(t) = f(t)$,
2. ${}^R I_t^\nu {}^C D_t^\nu f(t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!}$,
3. ${}^C D_t^\nu f(t) = {}^R I_t^{n-\nu} {}^C D_t^n f(t)$,
4. ${}^C D_t^\nu (\lambda f(t) + \theta g(t)) = \lambda {}^C D_t^\nu f(t) + \theta {}^C D_t^\nu g(t)$,
5. ${}^C D_t^\nu t^\beta = \begin{cases} 0, & \nu \in N_0, \beta < \nu, \\ \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\nu)} t^{\beta-\nu}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$
6. ${}^C D_t^\nu \lambda = 0$,

where λ, θ are real constants and $n - 1 < \nu \leq n$.

2.1 Wavelets and Chelyshkov wavelets

Wavelets have been very successfully used in many scientific and engineering fields. They constitute a family of functions constructed from dilation and translation of a signal function called the mother wavelet. When the dilation parameter a and the translation parameter b vary continuously, we have the following family of continuous wavelets

$$\psi_{a,b}(t) = |a|^{-\frac{1}{2}} \psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right), \quad a, b \in \mathbb{R}, a \neq 0.$$

If we restrict the parameters a and b to discrete values as $a = a_0^{-k}$, $b = nb_0 a_0^{-k}$, $a_0 > 1$, $b_0 > 0$, where n and k are positive integers, the family of discrete wavelets are defined as

$$\psi_{k,n}(t) = |a_0|^{k/2} \psi(a_0^k t - nb_0),$$

where $\psi_{k,n}(t)$ form a wavelet basis for $L^2(\mathbb{R})$. In particular, when $a_0 = 2$ and $b_0 = 1$, then $\psi_{k,n}(t)$ forms an orthonormal basis if

$$\langle \psi_{k,n}, \psi_{l,m} \rangle = \delta_{k,l} \delta_{n,m}.$$

The Chelyshkov wavelets are defined on $[0, 1)$ as [3]

$$\psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{2m+1} 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $m = 0, 1, \dots, \hat{m}; \hat{m} = M - 1; \hat{n} = n - 1; n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$ and $\hat{w} = 2^{k-1}M$. Also, $\mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(t)$ denotes the Chelyshkov polynomials defined on the interval $[0, 1]$ as [3]:

$$\mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(t) = \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} t^r, \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, \hat{m}. \quad (2)$$

The Chelyshkov polynomials are orthogonal on the interval $[0, 1]$ and their orthogonality condition is as follows [3]

$$\int_0^1 \mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(t) \mathcal{P}_{n,\hat{m}}(t) dt = \frac{\delta_{m,n}}{m+n+1},$$

where $\delta_{m,n}$ is Kronecker delta.

Also, we let

$$\Psi(t) = [\psi_{1,0,\hat{m}}(t), \psi_{1,1,\hat{m}}(t), \psi_{1,2,\hat{m}}(t), \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},M-1,\hat{m}}(t)]^T. \quad (3)$$

3 Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operator ${}^R_0 I_t^\nu$ for $\Psi(t)$ in Eq. (3) is given by

$${}^R_0 I_t^\nu \Psi(t) = R(t, \nu), \quad (4)$$

where

$$R(t, \nu) = [{}^R_0 I_t^\nu \psi_{1,0,\hat{m}}(t), {}^R_0 I_t^\nu \psi_{1,1,\hat{m}}(t), {}^R_0 I_t^\nu \psi_{1,2,\hat{m}}(t), \dots, {}^R_0 I_t^\nu \psi_{2^{k-1},M-1,\hat{m}}(t)]^T. \quad (5)$$

To obtain ${}^R_0 I_t^\nu \psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t)$, we use the Laplace transform. From Eq. (??), we get

$$\psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t) = \mu_{\frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}}}(t) \tau_{m,k} \mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}) - \mu_{\frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}}(t) \tau_{m,k} \mathcal{P}_{m,\hat{m}}(2^{k-1}t - \hat{n}), \quad (6)$$

where $\mu_\beta(t)$ is unit step function defined as

$$\mu_\beta(t) = \begin{cases} 1, & t \geq \beta, \\ 0, & t < \beta, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\tau_{m,k} = 2^{\frac{k-1}{2}} \sqrt{(2m+1)}.$$

By taking the Laplace transform from Eq. (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \ell[\psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t)] &= \tau_{m,k} e^{-\frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}}s} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \\ &\quad \frac{2^{(k-1)r} \Gamma(r+1)}{s^{r+1}} - \tau_{m,k} e^{-\frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}hs} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} \sum_{s=0}^{\lfloor r\lambda \rfloor} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \\ &\quad \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \binom{r}{s} \frac{2^{(k-1)(r-s)} \Gamma(r-s+1)}{s^{r-s+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

By using properties of Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\ell [{}_0^R I_t^\nu \psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t)] &= \ell \left[\frac{t^{\nu-1}}{\Gamma(\nu)} * {}_0^R I_t^\nu \psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t) \right] \\
&= \tau_{m,k} e^{-\frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}}s} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \frac{2^{(k-1)r}\Gamma(r+1)}{s^{r+\nu+1}} \\
&- \tau_{m,k} e^{-\frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}s} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} \sum_{s=0}^{\lfloor r \rfloor} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \\
&\quad \binom{r}{s} \frac{2^{(k-1)(r-s)}\Gamma(r-s+1)}{s^{r-s+\nu+1}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Taking the inverse Laplace transform from Eq. (8) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
{}_0^R I_t^\nu \psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t) &= \tau_{m,k} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \frac{2^{(k-1)r}\Gamma(r+1)}{m\Gamma(r+\nu+1)} \\
&\quad \left(t - \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \right)^{r+\nu} \mu_{\frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}}}(t) - \tau_{m,k} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} \sum_{s=0}^{\lfloor r \rfloor} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \\
&\quad \binom{r}{s} \frac{2^{(k-1)(r-s)}\Gamma(r-s+1)}{\Gamma(r-s+\nu+1)} \left(t - \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}} \right)^{r\nu-s+\nu} \mu_{\frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}}(t).
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

By considering, relation (9), we get

$${}_0^R I_t^\nu \psi_{n,m,\hat{m}}(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & 0 \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}}, \\ \tau_{m,k} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \frac{2^{(k-1)r}\Gamma(r+1)}{m\Gamma(r+\nu+1)} \left(t - \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \right)^{r+\nu}, & \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}}, \\ \tau_{m,k} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \frac{2^{(k-1)r}\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(r+\nu+1)} \\ \left(t - \frac{\hat{n}}{2^{k-1}} \right)^{r+\nu} - \tau_{m,k} \sum_{r=m}^{\hat{m}} \sum_{s=0}^{\lfloor r \rfloor} (-1)^{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}-m}{r-m} \binom{\hat{m}+r+1}{\hat{m}-m} \\ \binom{r}{s} \frac{2^{(k-1)(r-s)}\Gamma(r-s+1)}{\Gamma(r-s+\nu+1)} \left(t - \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}} \right)^{r\nu-s+\nu}, & \frac{\hat{n}+1}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < 1. \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

4 Problem statement and approximation method

Consider the FOCP

$$\min(\max) \quad J[u] = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), u(t)) dt, \tag{11}$$

subject to

$${}_0^C D_t^\nu x(t) = g(t, x(t)) + b(t)u(t), \quad n-1 \leq \nu \leq n, n = 2, 3, \dots \tag{12}$$

$$x(0) = x_0, x'(0) = x_1, \dots, x^{(\lceil \nu \rceil - 1)}(0) = x_{\lceil \nu \rceil - 1}.$$

Here f, g and $b \neq 0$ are smooth functions of their arguments. Computing the control function from relation (12) and substituting into the performance index J yields

$$\min(\max) J[x] = \int_0^1 f(t, x(t), \frac{1}{b(t)}({}^C D_t^\nu x(t) - g(t, x(t))))dt, \quad (13)$$

$$x(0) = x_0, x'(0) = x_1, \dots, x^{([\nu]-1)}(0) = x_{[\nu]-1}.$$

Now we solve the optimization problem (13) via fractional-order Chelyshkov wavelets approximation. First, we approximate $D^\nu x(t)$ and $x(t)$ as

$${}^C D_t^\nu x(t) \simeq C^T \Psi(t), \quad x(t) \simeq C^T R(t, \nu) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i. \quad (14)$$

By substituting the approximations (14) in the performance index (13), our aim is to optimize the functional of $\hat{m} = 2^{k-1}M$ variables, $c_j; j = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{m}$ as

$$\min(\max) J[C] = \int_0^1 f(t, C^T R(t, \nu) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i, \frac{1}{b(t)}(C^T \Psi(t) - g(t, C^T R(t, \nu) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i)))dt.$$

For simplicity, we let

$$\min(\max) J[C] = \int_0^1 Q(t, C)dt, \quad (15)$$

where

$$Q(t, C) = f(t, C^T R(t, \nu) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i, \frac{1}{b(t)}(C^T \Psi(t) - g(t, C^T R(t, \nu) + \sum_{i=0}^{[\nu]-1} \frac{t^i}{i!} x_i))).$$

The Gaussian quadrature formula is used to approximate the integration in Eq. (15). We get

$$J[c] = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^M \omega_i Q(\frac{\tau_i + 1}{2}, C), \quad (16)$$

where $\tau_i; i = 1, 2, \dots, M$; are zeros of Legendre polynomial $P_M(t)$ and $\omega_i = \frac{-2}{(M+1)P'_M(\tau_i)P_{M+1}(\tau_i)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, M$.

The necessary conditions for extremum of J are given by

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial c_i}[C] = 0, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, \hat{m}.$$

The above relations can be solved for C using the Newton's iterative method.

5 Applications and numerical results

Example 5.1. Consider the following linear optimal control problem to minimize the functional [1]

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [(x(t) - t^{\nu+1})^2 + (u(t) - t^{\nu+1} - \Gamma^2(\nu + 2)t)^2]dt, \quad (17)$$

subject to the dynamical system

$${}^C D_t^\nu x(t) = (-x(t) + u(t))/\Gamma(\nu + 2), \quad x(0) = 0. \quad (18)$$

The exact solution for this FOCP is given by

$$x(t) = t^{\nu+1}, \quad u(t) = t^{\nu+1} + \Gamma^2(\nu + 2)t.$$

Table 1: Absolute errors of $x(t)$ at $\nu = 0.7$ for Example 1.

t	<i>MADM</i>		<i>VIM</i>		<i>Present method</i> $k = 2, M = 4$
	$N = 5$	$N = 10$	$N = 5$	$N = 10$	
0.1	6.60×10^{-4}	6.87×10^{-15}	2.12×10^{-4}	6.85×10^{-15}	3.47×10^{-18}
0.2	1.04×10^{-3}	2.86×10^{-12}	3.53×10^{-4}	2.86×10^{-12}	0
0.3	1.36×10^{-3}	9.73×10^{-11}	4.88×10^{-4}	9.73×10^{-11}	0
0.4	1.68×10^{-3}	1.19×10^{-9}	6.42×10^{-4}	1.19×10^{-9}	2.78×10^{-17}
0.5	2.03×10^{-3}	8.28×10^{-9}	8.47×10^{-4}	8.28×10^{-9}	5.55×10^{-17}
0.6	2.47×10^{-3}	4.05×10^{-8}	1.16×10^{-3}	4.05×10^{-8}	0
0.7	3.09×10^{-3}	1.55×10^{-7}	1.65×10^{-3}	1.55×10^{-7}	2.22×10^{-16}
0.8	4.01×10^{-3}	4.94×10^{-7}	2.45×10^{-3}	4.94×10^{-7}	2.22×10^{-16}
0.9	5.38×10^{-3}	1.38×10^{-6}	3.70×10^{-3}	1.38×10^{-6}	3.33×10^{-16}
J	6.15×10^{-6}	3.23×10^{-13}	4.13×10^{-6}	3.23×10^{-13}	1.06×10^{-31}

Table 2: Absolute errors of $u(t)$ at $\nu = 0.7$ for Example 1.

t	<i>MADM</i>		<i>VIM</i>		<i>Present method</i> $k = 2, M = 4$
	$N = 5$	$N = 15$	$N = 5$	$N = 10$	
0.1	1.08×10^{-3}	3.86×10^{-9}	1.72×10^{-3}	3.91×10^{-9}	1.11×10^{-16}
0.2	1.29×10^{-3}	7.64×10^{-9}	1.93×10^{-3}	7.69×10^{-9}	1.11×10^{-16}
0.3	1.53×10^{-3}	1.11×10^{-8}	2.13×10^{-3}	1.15×10^{-8}	0
0.4	1.78×10^{-3}	1.52×10^{-8}	2.33×10^{-3}	1.53×10^{-8}	0
0.5	2.00×10^{-3}	1.90×10^{-8}	2.50×10^{-3}	1.90×10^{-8}	4.44×10^{-16}
0.6	2.16×10^{-3}	2.28×10^{-8}	2.58×10^{-3}	2.28×10^{-8}	0
0.7	2.17×10^{-3}	2.66×10^{-8}	2.51×10^{-3}	2.66×10^{-8}	4.44×10^{-16}
0.8	1.93×10^{-3}	2.04×10^{-8}	2.16×10^{-3}	3.04×10^{-8}	4.44×10^{-16}
0.9	1.27×10^{-3}	3.41×10^{-8}	1.39×10^{-3}	3.41×10^{-8}	1.33×10^{-15}

Figure 1: Numerical solutions with $k = 2$, $M = 4$ and $\nu = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1$ for Example 1.

The absolute errors of the state variable $x(t)$ and the control variable $u(t)$ obtained using variational iteration method (VIM) and modification Adomian decomposition method (MADM) [1] and the present method at $\nu = 0.7$ are displayed in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Also Figures 1(a) and (b) show the behavior of the numerical solutions of the state variable $x(t)$ and the control variable $u(t)$, respectively.

Example 5.2. Consider the following problem to minimize the functional [1]

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 [x^2(t) + u^2(t)] dt, \quad (19)$$

subject to the dynamical system

$${}^C_0 D_t^\nu x(t) = -0.25(x(t) - u(t)) + t^\nu, \quad x(0) = 1. \quad (20)$$

The exact solution for this FOCP is given by

$$x(t) = \frac{(\sqrt{2}e^{\sqrt{2}t/4} - e^{\sqrt{2}t/4})(9e^{-\sqrt{2}/4} + 2\sqrt{2} + 2) - (\sqrt{2}e^{-\sqrt{2}t/4} + e^{-\sqrt{2}t/4})(-9e^{\sqrt{2}/4} + 2\sqrt{2} - 2)}{(\sqrt{2}-1)e^{-\sqrt{2}/4} + (\sqrt{2}+1)e^{\sqrt{2}/4}} + 2t - 8,$$

$$u(t) = \frac{e^{\sqrt{2}t/4}(9e^{-\sqrt{2}/4} + 2\sqrt{2} + 2) + e^{-\sqrt{2}t/4}(-9e^{\sqrt{2}/4} + 2\sqrt{2} - 2)}{(\sqrt{2}-1)e^{-\sqrt{2}/4} + (\sqrt{2}+1)e^{\sqrt{2}/4}} - 2t.$$

In Table 3, a comparison is made between the values of J obtained by VIM and MADM [1] with $N = 10$, together with the present method with $k = 1$, $M = 7$ and different values of ν . Figures 2(a) and (b) show the approximation of the state variable $x(t)$ and the control variable $u(t)$, respectively, for various values of ν with $k = 1$, $M = 7$, and we can conclude the convergence of these values as ν approaches 1.

Table 3: The optimal values of cost function J for various choices of ν with $k = 1$, $M = 7$ for Example 2.

t	$\nu = 1$	$\nu = 0.99$	$\nu = 0.9$	$\nu = 0.8$
<i>Ref.</i> [1]	0.535837	0.538097	0.561228	0.593473
<i>Present method</i>	0.535837	0.538097	0.561190	0.593301

Example 5.3. Consider the following fractional optimal control problem ([1], [2])

$$J = \int_0^1 [(x_1(t) - 1 - t^{\frac{3}{2}})^2 + (x_2(t) - t^{\frac{5}{2}})^2 + (u(t) - \frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{4}t + t^{\frac{5}{2}})^2] dt, \quad (21)$$

subject to the dynamical system

$${}^C_0 D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} x_1(t) = x_2(t) + u(t), \quad (22)$$

Figure 2: Numerical solutions with $k = 1$, $M = 7$ and $\nu = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9, 1$ for Example 2.

$${}^C D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} x_2(t) = x_1(t) + \frac{15\sqrt{\pi}}{16} t^2 - t^{\frac{3}{2}} - 1, \quad (23)$$

The exact solution for this FOCP is given by

$$x_1(t) = 1 + t^{\frac{3}{2}}, \quad x_2(t) = t^{\frac{5}{2}}, \quad u(t) = \frac{3\sqrt{\pi}}{4} t - t^{\frac{5}{2}}.$$

In Table 4, we compare the optimal values of cost function J obtained using MADM method [1], the Epsilon-Ritz method [2] with present method for $k = 1$, $M = 5$. In Figs 3(a), (b) and (c) we plot the absolute errors of $x_1(t)$, $x_2(t)$ and $u(t)$, respectively.

Table 4: The optimal values of cost function J for $k = 1$, $M = 5$ obtained for Example 3

	<i>Epsilon – Ritz method</i>	<i>MADM</i>	<i>Present method</i>	<i>Exact</i>
J	8.00×10^{-6}	$3.69 \times 10^{-5} (N = 10)$ $4.12 \times 10^{-12} (N = 20)$ $8.47 \times 10^{-17} (N = 30)$	1.18×10^{-31}	0

Figure 3: Absolute errors of (a) : $x_1(t)$, (b) : $x_2(t)$, (c) : $u(t)$ with $k = 1$, $M = 5$ for Example 3.

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